

GENERALIZED PLANE STRAIN EFFECTS ON DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITE NOTCHED TENSILE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

A composite material notched tensile beam (NTB) has been modeled by finite elements to study the effects of generalized plane strain loading on delamination. The NTB is a lower-order analog of a composite pressure vessel containing an external part-through hole. Generalized plane strain loading is intended to approximate the bi-axial loading of pressure vessels. Strain energy release rates have been determined as a function of delamination length for an S-glass/epoxy NTB with uni-directional $[0^\circ]_8$ and multi-directional $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, +77^\circ, -77^\circ]_2$ layups. Single delaminations located at the notch bottom for 3- and 4-ply deep notches have been modeled. Results for the generalized plane strain solutions are not dramatically different from the plane strain solutions.

Keywords: delamination, notched tensile beam, strain energy release rates, part-through hole

1. INTRODUCTION

Cylindrical pressure vessels made from fiber reinforced composite materials are used in a variety of aerospace and industrial applications. The failure of such vessels in the presence of part-through flaws is a complex process that is difficult to characterize both experimentally and analytically. The motivation for the present work is the particular problem presented when the flaw is a steadily deepening external part-through hole, such as that created by progressive material removal due to laser ablation. Similar flaws could also result from impact damage or even as an intentional manufactured or machined feature. The presence of a part-through hole in a cylindrical composite laminate gives rise to stress/strain concentration and interlaminar stresses at the 'free edge' which lead to very complicated three-dimensional stress fields. Failure of the structure is therefore likely to follow a complex, multi-mode process. Failure modes can nevertheless be grouped into two broad categories: (1) in-plane failure within plies (matrix cracking & splitting, fiber fracture/breakage, ply degradation); and (2) out-of-plane failure between plies (primarily delamination fracture). Ultimate failure will consist of some combination of these failure modes and will be greatly influenced by the relative contributions, interactions, and sequence of events. The overall goal of the current research effort is to provide more in-depth understanding of these failure processes by developing modeling procedures that include both failure modes explicitly.

In the initial phases of this work, a simplified model is being studied which is analogous in many aspects of its mechanics to the cylindrical pressure vessel with an external part-through hole. The notched tensile beam (NTB) is defined schematically in Figure 1 and has been studied previously both analytically and experimentally for this purpose [1,2]. This configuration can be treated as a two-dimensional problem and modeled in much greater detail than the fully three-dimensional structure. The delamination crack in the specimen is assumed to initiate and grow from the notch region and extend completely through the width of the specimen. Only half of the specimen is shown since the left end represents a plane of symmetry. The model is loaded with a tensile concentrated force P directed along its primary axis. The focus at this stage is on modeling and characterizing delamination, without including the effects of in-plane failures yet. The philosophy has been to first establish detailed procedures for modeling delaminations and seek to understand more fully the effects of factors such as notch depth, material systems & layups, and curvature on delamination before incorporating in-plane failure into the model.

Previous studies of straight NTB models have examined Kevlar/epoxy and S-glass/epoxy materials with delaminations at the notch bottom as well as at ply interfaces 'above' the notch bottom [2]. Since the problem of interest is a cylindrical filament-wound structure, the effects of curvature have also been investigated by modeling curved NTB configurations [3]. The view of Figure 1 represents an idealized view of a plane of cross-section through the cylinder with the long axis of the NTB aligned in the hoop, or circumferential, direction. The load P then represents loading corresponding to the hoop stresses created due to the internal pressure. Closed cylindrical pressure vessels actually present bi-axial loading due to both hoop and longitudinal stresses. The current study was undertaken to include loading in the longitudinal direction by adding generalized plane strain loading to the two-dimensional NTB model.

Figure 1. Notched tensile beam (NTB) configuration and nomenclature.

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

Numerical solutions for curved NTB models were obtained using standard displacement based finite element methods. A sample finite element mesh is presented in Figure 2. The geometry, meshing, boundary conditions, loading, and material properties were created and specified using PATRAN Plus [4], while the actual analysis was accomplished using ABAQUS [5]. Eight-noded isoparametric continuum elements with reduced integration (2x2) have been employed. Plane strain assumptions were used for one set of solutions and generalized plane strain conditions were used for a corresponding set of solutions. In general, the finite element mesh consisted of approximately 1950 elements and 6250 nodes. Static, geometrically nonlinear analysis was employed. Specimen dimensions (see Figure 1) were as follows: notch width - $d=0.50\text{cm}$, total length - $l=9.9764\text{cm}$, and height - $h=0.2235\text{cm}$. The material was S-glass/epoxy and the specimen was considered to be composed of a total of eight plies with each ply 0.02794cm thick. Delaminations were at the notch bottom only ($c=s$) as indicated by the arrow in Figure 2(b.). Two notch depths were studied: 3-ply deep ($s=0.08382\text{cm}$, $s/h=3/8$); and 4-ply deep ($s=0.11176\text{cm}$, $s/h=1/2$). Two layup cases were also examined: (1) a uni-directional $[0^\circ]_8$ model, which corresponds to a cylinder with all plies oriented with the fiber in the 'hoop' direction; and (2) a multi-directional $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, +77^\circ, -77^\circ]_2$ model, which represents a cylinder with alternating hoop and helical plies.

Figure 2. Sample finite element mesh for curved NTB models.

- (a.) Full view of entire model.
- (b.) Close-up of notch and delamination.

Loading for the curved NTB models was not applied as a direct concentrated force P but rather as a uniformly distributed pressure along the inner circumference of the model. All nodes on either 'end' of the model were constrained to have zero displacement in the hoop direction but were free to displace in the radial direction. The pressure was 10.04MPa which created a net section force (equivalent to P) of 13,459N. For generalized plane strain conditions, each element is defined to have an extra node, which is common to all elements. Each element also has displacements in the out-of-plane direction but they are constrained to the common extra node. Strains in the out-of-plane direction are then applied as prescribed displacements of the extra node. The formulation also allows for loading the extra node with a concentrated force in the out-of-plane direction. This option was used in the present study to apply a longitudinal section force corresponding to the longitudinal stresses created by an internal pressure of 10.04MPa in an un-notched cylinder. The driving force for delamination crack growth was determined by calculating the strain energy release rate at the crack tip for each crack length using the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [6,7].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solutions were obtained for delamination lengths of 0.00694cm, 0.0139cm, 0.0208cm, 0.0347cm, 0.0833cm, 0.125cm, and 0.250cm. These lengths represent length-to-thickness ratios (l/h) of 0.031, 0.062, 0.093, 0.155, 0.376, 0.559, and 1.118, respectively. Strain energy release rates as a function of delamination length are summarized in Figure 3 for the 3-ply deep notch case. The dashed lines are for conventional plane strain (P.S.) conditions and the solid lines for generalized plane strain (G.P.S.). Strain energy release rates are considerably higher for the multi-directional models as compared to the uni-directional models. The initial drop followed by a slight increase and leveling off of energy release rates is consistent with the pattern observed in previous similar studies [2,3].

Figure 3. Total strain energy release rates (G_T) for 3-ply deep cases.

The differences between the plane strain (P.S.) and generalized plane strain (G.P.S.) conditions appear somewhat surprisingly to be only minimal and probably not very significant practically. It is interesting to note, however, that the additional out-of-plane loading from the generalized plane strain case results in an increase in strain energy release rates for the uni-directional models, but a slight decrease in values for the multi-directional models. Further insight into this behavior can be gained by considering the separate mode I and II components of the total strain energy release rate. The total (G_T), mode I (G_I), and mode II (G_{II}) components are presented in Figures 4 and 5 for the 3-ply uni-directional and multi-directional cases, respectively. The overall increase for the generalized plane strain case for the uni-directional models (Figure 4) appears to be due almost exclusively to an increase in the mode II component, whereas the mode I component remains about the same. The mode II component increases similarly for the multi-directional case (Figure 5) but the mode I component decreases in this case. The decrease in mode I dominates and accounts for the overall decrease in the total strain energy release rates for the multi-directional models.

The plots of Figure 6 compare the 3- and 4-ply deep notch results for the multi-directional models only. A general increase in total strain energy release rates is apparent for the deeper notch (4-ply) as would be expected, but the generalized plane strain conditions result in an increase in G_T for the 4-ply multi-directional case as compared to the corresponding conventional plane strain case. The reason for this behavior is currently being investigated. Besides the obvious difference in notch depth, the two cases also differ in the constitution of the plies bounding the delamination crack. For the 3-ply deep models, the delamination is between '+' and '-' 77° plies, while the crack is between a 77° ply and a 0° ply for the 4-ply deep case.

Figure 4. Total (G_T), mode I (G_I), and mode II (G_{II}) strain energy release rates for 3-ply uni-directional models (P.S.-plane strain; G.P.S.-generalized plane strain).

Figure 5. Total (G_T), mode I (G_I), and mode II (G_{II}) strain energy release rates for 3-ply multi-directional models (P.S.-plane strain; G.P.S.-generalized plane strain).

Figure 6. Total strain energy release rates (G_T) for 3- and 4-ply deep multi-directional models (P.S.-plane strain; G.P.S.-generalized plane strain).

4. CLOSURE

A composite notched tensile beam with 3- and 4-ply deep notches has been studied under plane strain conditions and generalized plane strain conditions. Strain energy release rates for delamination cracks emanating from the notch bottom have been compared. Even though the generalized plane strain loading creates out-of-plane loads high enough to simulate longitudinal stresses in a pressurized cylindrical structure, strain energy release rates are not dramatically different than for plane strain conditions. The effect of generalized plane strain loading can either increase or decrease strain energy release rates slightly depending on the notch depth and the layup of plies bounding the delamination.

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